

THE SIGNIFICANCE OF ANALYSING THE LITERARY WORKS IN UZBEK AND ENGLISH LITERATURE (BASED ON THE TRAGEDIES “OTHELLO” BY W. SHAKESPEARE AND “MIRZO ULUGBEK” BY M. SHAYKHZODA)

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Abstract:

This article deals with the importance of analyzing literary works, the role of comparative studies in both linguistics and literature through two preeminent tragedies of English and Uzbek literature “Othello” and “Mirzo Ulugbek”. The purpose of this study and research is to analyze the linguistic, lingua-semantic and lingua-cultural features of these two plays. The primary reason for doing this research is to learn the Uzbek and English nations’ literature comparatively by analyzing their lexical resources and their usage in works, descriptions of characters emotions and events in both tragic plays.

Key words: Comparative study, tragedy, research, primary reason, lingua-semantic, lingua-cultural feature.

doi: <https://doi.org/10.2024/oyz9vg44>

Literary analysis is the examination and evaluation of a literary work. When people analyze literature, they think how the author used literary strategies to create meaning. Readers first critically read the text and examine elements like figurative language, syntax, diction, and structure. When looking at these elements, readers consider how the author used them to create meaning. They then make analytical claims about the text they can support by discussing specific evidence from the work [5.1]. It is clear that analysis is focused on learning different features of works by dividing them into small parts, finding the differences and similarities of these parts by comparing and contrasting. Some people compare the literary works with the parts of the body which cannot be separated one part from another and they refuse the comparative analysis, while others consider that it is impossible to learn any sphere of life without comparing one to another. According to the points stated above, it is obvious that the purpose of analyzing the literary works first to understand it, then evaluate it from different points of view. Analysis of literary works includes several types, such as: sociological analysis which directs the researchers to learn and comprehend the events happened in the work and real life, how they are connected to each other, what are relationships between them, how real they are according to the historical facts. While studying these two works, researcher will have a chance to learn the individual features and abilities of two authors, their attitude towards the events and characters in both plays, and also evaluate two nations behavior, traditions and cultural habits. Comparing only two characters of these two plays, we can find deep logical connectivity of works, although the events describe different periods of life.

William Shakespeare’s classic tragedy “Othello” has been the focal point of a large variety of critical literary discussions since its first performance in 1604 due to its complex

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and nuanced portrayal of humanity[1.2]. During the research, it can be found that there are still a number of mysteries and misunderstandings of this work among scientists and linguists, which means why it is important to analyze the literature, to learn it comparatively. The play starts with Iago's announcement of hatred for his general Othello, a Moor (dark-skinned). The reason for this hatred is that Othello promoted Cassio as his lieutenant, in place of Iago. Because of this, Iago felt himself as an enemy for Othello, after that. Desdemona, the woman whom Othello loved and married, his father Brabantio who was really against their marriage, a Venetian senator, Rodrigo, a Venetian gentleman, and Emilia, Iago's wife, Desdemona's attendant are the main characters of the play. During the play, Iago does a lot of betrayals against Othello, and it causes severe pain and annoyance and misunderstandings among characters.

Act 1, Scene 1: Iago

Despise me

If I do not. Three great ones of the city

Off-capped to him and by the faith of man

I know my price, I am worth no worse a place

But he (as loving his own pride and purposes)

Evades them with a bombast circumstances

Horribly stuffed with epithets of war

And in conclusion

Nonsuits my mediators. For "Certes" says he

"I have already chosen my officer".

And what was he [2.7].

In this piece of play, it is seen that people have different faces which show others differently in many situations. Friendship turned into hatred and jealousy because of positions. Unfortunately, Othello still believes him as his close person. This play was written during the 16th century, but these feelings and emotions are being renowned daily by many people.

Maksud Shaykhzoda is a world famous Uzbek and Azerbaijan poet, scientist and interpreter, the author of variety of popular manuscripts, such as the tragedy of "Mirzo Ulugbek". He tried to connect the spirit of past and the future in his works [3.1]. "Mirzo Ulugbek" is one of his famous works describes the life and tragic death of the king and scientist Mirzo Ulugbek. While comparing these two plays, it can be analysed that readers can easily find the betrayal and jealousy, but when it is done by your own child it is another topic to discuss. Othello saw this betrayal by his friend Iago, but for Mirzo Ulugbek it is his own son, Abdullatif, who wanted to achieve the throne by killing his own father. In both plays, promotion was one of the main reasons for lots of loss, hatred and grief. Cultures may not be an obstacle in such situations, although there are lots of friends and acquaintances around you, if you feel this pain because of your closest people, it hurts you severely. Tragic ending scenes of both plays make the readers think deeply. Analyzing literature allows readers to articulate their interpretation of a text. To interpret literature, readers should consider elements like the following [4.5].

Literary elements Definition Sample analytical questions

Characters People in the story How do the characters change throughout the story?

Do the characters represent universal ideas or qualities?

Figurative language The use of words beyond their literal definitions. Types include simile, metaphor, and personification. How does figurative language impact the meaning of the text?

How are types of figurative language related to other literary elements?

Plot The events of the story What is the main conflict?

How does the author build feelings like suspense and confusion through the plot?

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Comparative literature promotes understanding and value for different world literatures by providing critical, social, sociological and methodical framework for analysis, as it is stated in the table, there are some exact questions to answer in the criteria of analyzing and comparing literary works which frame your research appropriately for the requirements.

References:

- [1]. Aida Sakina-Safer, "Othello, racial themes and Public reception: Analysis of literary criticism since its release", June 2022
- [2]. Javlon Jovliev, "Central Asian literature and Shaykhzoda", 2023
- [3]. Maksud Shaykhzoda, "Mirzo Ulugbek", 2019
- [4]. William Shakespeare, "The tragedy of Othello, The Moor of Venice", 1623
- [5]. <https://www.studysmarter.co.uk/explanations/english/research-and-composition/literary-analysis/>